

A Study on the perception of students from Hnet-Aw-San boys' training school towards their living situation and training

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Abstract

The main focus of this study is to investigate the perception of the Juvenile Offenders (JO) and Street Children (SC) regarding living situation and trainings in "Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School". There were 100 respondents (50 Juvenile Offenders and 50 Street Children) of age 13 and above. Altogether, there are about 500 students in the school. The sample size of 100 students can only cover the one-fifth of student population. Qualitative data are collected by means of in-depth interview method using structured questionnaire. The main focus of this questionnaire was laid upon the perception on the living situation in the school and on trainings in "Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School". A questionnaire including 34 items was used as an instrument. There is positive perception of students from "Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School" towards their living situation and trainings. Nevertheless, some JO have negative perception towards the living situation because more of them had lived with their families and better situations before they were sent to this school. There is a difference in perception between JO group and SC group towards their current accommodations. There are different forms of satisfaction between JO group and SC group towards food hygienic. That "Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School" is doing its best to purely take the form of training school for boys who commit the offence against the law will be pointed in this study. During the transaction period between child correction center and training school, there are lots of struggle for handling kids and follow the newly set procedures.

Introduction

In Myanmar, there is a school that cares and trains for Juvenile Offenders and Street Children. It is located in Kawt-Mhu Township, Yanogn Region. The study focused on **Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School** which is running under the administration of "Department of Social Welfare, Ministry of Social Welfare". Campus of it is about 36.02 acres wide.

The origin of the school dated back to British Rule and it was founded on 1st June, 1930 in Tha-Yat, Called "Borstal and Senior Training School" for Juvenile Offenders. When the country gained its independence from the British, it was moved to Paung-Tae as a child detention center and then, moved again to Thar-Yar-Waddy in 1951. In 1957, it was moved back to its original place, Tha-Yat. In 1972, it was moved to this current place which used to be an orphanage home, so the name of the school is changed to "Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School." It is only for boys so that since 1973 to date boys of about 9600 are well-trained to become good citizens although there is about 4 to 7% of annual runaway rate. The five objectives mentioned together with its visionary mission, "Being in service for the best interest of the child" are as follows:

1. to implement for the children to get full rights as Child Law, 1993 initially stated,
2. to give protection and feed children who need care so that they are sent to the school by authority (according to Child Law, 1993)
3. to detain juvenile offenders and do correction their character.
4. to do appropriate protective school activities for each child who are being detained in the school to be such a place of warmth and protection, and
5. not only to teach children formal education but also to give other vocational trainings to develop their physical, mental and intellectual skills and characters and to train them to be a good citizens.

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There are altogether 47 staff appointed according to the structure and its organo-gram but there are 43 current official staff and net manpower by which it is run is about 37, rental staff are 7. The capacity to accept children are 500 and there are now 472 children detained hosting in 7 wards. The wards for criminal children are Anawrahta, Kyansittha, Bandoola and those for street children are, Tabinshwehtee, Aungzeya, Bayintnaung and Minyekyawswa which is for the schooling children of both categories. Generally 75 children stay at each ward.

The **eight core programs** implemented in the school are: (1) Training, (2) Education, (3) Health, (4) Nutrition, (5) Physical and Mental Development, (6) Entertainment, (7) Restore Family Link, and (8) Religion & Culture.

Causes of Juvenile Delinquency

The causes and conditions of juvenile crime are usually found at each level of social structure, including society as a whole, social institutions, social groups and organizations, and interpersonal relationship. Juveniles' choice of delinquent careers and the consequent perpetuation of delinquency are fostered by a wide range of factors. Cultural factors, urbanization, family, media and peer influence are the most important factors to cause juvenile delinquency.

Juvenile delinquency is driven by the negative consequences of social and economic development, in particular economic crises, political instability, and the weakening of major institutions (including the State, systems of public education and public assistance, and the family.) Juvenile delinquents, who commit offences under existing law, are termed as Juvenile Offenders.

Causes of becoming street children

A single cause such as extreme poverty, civil wars, or natural disasters might be the cause often that leads to a single child ending up being on the street. Emergence and development of the problem of street children can be divided into two main factors: paving or indirect causes (low income and education level of the family, family breakdown, dropping out of schools, family size) which pave the way for the emergence of the phenomenon; and direct and immediate causes which lead to the problem of the child residing on the street away from home, which were indicated by street children themselves as reasons for being on the street.

Street children tend to settle down in areas where they feel secure, protected from violence, and with the possibility of earning a living and having fun. These areas are popular districts where their existence does not upset the local inhabitants, popular areas full of shops and workshops and shelter, markets and commercial areas, free public gardens, near train stations, bus stops and terminals, areas with special socio-cultural characteristics where they can beg people for money, under bridges and on the flyovers, the cemetery and wasteland where they can earn a living in doing minor jobs and easily find their basic needs for cheap food.

Government Organizations (GOs) and Non-Government Organizations' (NGOs) Activities / Services Targeting JO & Sc

The following points have been implemented by GOs and NGOs dealing with the issue of JO & SC.

1. Family Reunion
2. Literacy education
3. Health programmes
4. Vocational Training
5. Child rights & protectiod

General Objective

The main objective of the study is to find out positive or negative perception of students from Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School towards their living situation and training during their stay in school.

Methodology

Participants

A total number of one hundred students from Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School were used as subjects. The age range of subject is 13 to 18 years old. Fifty students were selected from juvenile offenders group and other fifty from street children group.

Instrument

"Perception on the Living Situation and Training" questionnaire was constructed. It was self-reported questionnaire based on five factors relevant to the conditions of health, education living standard, vocational training and recreation activities. The questionnaire includes 34 questions and it took about half an hour for each student to answer.

Procedure

The test was administered to the students (including juvenile offenders and street children), age from 13 to 18 years old, by using structured interview based on questionnaire because most students were having low level education and they were not able to respond the items in questionnaire easily. Then, the collecting data will be computed by using descriptive statistics.

Results and discussion

In this section the results of the data are presented and the findings are discussed. The obtaining data were analyzed according to the perception of respondents towards their nutrition, accommodation, trainings, and recreation activities.

Table (1) Types of crime committed by Juvenile offenders

Types of Crimes	f	%
1. Theft	31	62
2. Murder	1	2
3. Hurt	4	8
4. Rape	8	16
5. Drugs	2	4
6. Others	4	8
Total	50	100

Figure (1) Types of committed Crimes

Types of crime committed by juvenile offenders were mentioned in the above table (1). Among them 31 offenders (62%) committed theft, 8 offenders (16%) committed rape case, 4 (8%) committed hurt, 2 (4%) involved in drug related areas and 1 (2%) committed murder. Four (8%) of them involved other offence types.

Table (2) Do you like the nutrition offered by the Training School?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	33	66	48	96	81	81
No	17	34	2	4	19	19

Table (2) pointed out the students' satisfaction on nutrition offered by training school. Thirty-three JO (66%) and forty-eight SC (96%) are satisfied with the provided nutrition. Seventeen JO (34%) and two SC (4%) are not satisfied with the nutrition. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 81% and that of 'No' response is 19%.

Table (3) Are you satisfied with the present accommodation provided by school?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	31	62	45	90	76	76
No	19	38	5	10	24	24

In table (3), 31 JO (62%) and 45 SC (90%) are satisfied with the present accommodation provided by school but 19 JO (38%) and 5 SC (10%) dislike it. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 76% and that of 'No' response is 24%.

Table (4) Do you like the clothes provided by school?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	39	78	47	94	86	86
No	11	22	3	6	14	14

From this table (4), it can be seen 39 JO (78%) and 47 SC (94%) response they like the clothes provided by school. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 86% and that of 'No' response is 14%.

Table (5) Are you satisfied with the health care service of the school?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	43	86	45	90	88	88
No	7	14	5	10	12	12

From this table (5), 43 JO (86%) are satisfied with the health care services. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 88% and that of 'No' response is 12%.

Table (6) Do you think the foods are hygienic?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	26	52	50	100	76	76
No	24	48	0	0	24	24

According to table (6), there are altogether 26 JO (52%) and 50 SC (100%) think that the food hygienic. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 76% and that of 'No' response is 24%.

Table (7) Do you like the seasonal events and sport competitions held by school?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	49	98	50	100	99	99
No	1	2	0	0	1	1

Based on the responses from the table (7), 49 JO (98%) and all the 50 SC (100%) like the seasonal events and sport competition held by school. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 99% and that of 'No' response is 1%.

Table (8) Are you satisfied with the ways of recreation during your leisure time?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	45	90	49	98	94	94
No	5	10	1	2	6	6

What we can see from this table (8) is that 45 JO (90%) and 49 SC (98%) are satisfied with the ways of recreation during their leisure. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 94% and that of 'No' response is 6%.

Table (9) Do you like the excursion arranged by the volunteer associations?

Response	JO		SC		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	45	90	48	96	93	93
No	5	10	2	4	7	7

According to the responses from the table (9), 45 JO (90%) and 48 SC (96%) like the excursion programmes arranged by the school. The total percentage on the 'Yes' response is 93% and that of 'No' response is 7%.

Discussion

Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School is a training school for juvenile offenders and street children under guidance of social welfare department. Social Welfare Department is helping the people in need especially people with disability and children in need of special care and protection. Hnet-Aw-San Boys' Training School focuses on providing services for the children in need of special care and protection.

This discussion is mainly based on the data collected from a hundred students of the school, 50 from juvenile offenders and 50 from street children. It can be found that theft is committed by most of the juvenile offenders. (table-1) The main reason why they committed theft case might be family poverty and imitation of friend behaviors. Basic needs of students (nutrition, accommodation and clothes) are provided by the school. It is found out that two-third of the JO and almost all SC are satisfied with the provisions (table-2, 3, and 4).

According to the data concerning their health, it is found out that 7 JO (14%) and 5 SC (10%) had minor illness and other health problems. Skin infections such as scabies are common because they have to share their clothes with each other; they have poor knowledge of personal hygiene care and lack of individual caregiver (table-5). According to the table - 6, 24 (48%) of JO perceived that provided foods are not hygienic. Most of JO had lived with their parents before they were sent to this school. Comparing with home-made food, the food provided by school is not clean and hygienic. SC had struggle for a meal themselves before they were sent here and so they have more positive perception towards food provided by school.

Both all JO (100%) and SC (98%) love to participate in and enjoy those events happily (table-7). According to responses, students like football and musical entertainment very much. Students' perception on leisure activities provided by the school is quite good because JO (90%) and SC (98%)

answered that they are fully satisfied on it (table-8). Annual excursions or trips arranged by the school are quite enjoyed by almost all JO (90%) & SC (96%) (table-9). Those activities are effective and have great impact on their spiritual comfort and physical health and they also get chances to learn new experience and knowledge.

Conclusion

As the main focus of the study is to find out the perception of the students, we studied their living situation such as accommodation, food and clothing provided by the school. We also studied their perception towards their educational and vocational trainings. According to our findings, it can be concluded that subjects of 50 JO exposed highly to commit crimes of theft, rapes and hurts but rarely to do robbery and political crimes. Most JO used to stay with families while almost all SC stayed with others before they were sent to this school. There are lesser complaints regarding on accommodation, food and clothing by SC. Relatively the JO have much more complaints on accommodation, food and clothes provided by school. So the perception of two groups is somewhat different up to their living situations.

References

- Consortium for Street Children, 2009:** Street Children Statistics, www.street-children.org.uk/uploads/resources/Street_Children_Stats_FINAL.pdf.
- Gretch Ellis, (1997-1999):** "Characteristics of Juvenile Offenders": Finding and Recommendations: 1992-1993 Riak and Need Study for the Juvenile Advisory Committee of The Charlottesville/ Albemarle Commission on Children and Families, Charlottesville, Virginia.
www.ccfinfo.org/PFDs/jj_prof_juvoff97_99.pdf
- Juvenile at the Training School, (2008):** Rhode Island KIDS COUNT fact book, www.rikidscount.org/matriarch/documents
- Marie Wernham, (2004):** An Outside Chance: Street Children and Juvenile Justice- International Perspective, Consortium for Street Children, www.crim.Org/docs.
- World Youth Report, (2003):** "Juvenile Delinquency" (Chapter 7), www.un.org/esa/socdev/unyin/documents/ch07.pdf